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Essentials of Teacher-Student Relationship in Human Capital Development

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ABSTRACT

Teaching and learning in educational institutions is one social practice where innovations are norms and one practice and innovation that is at the heart of teaching and learning is teacher student relationship. Teacher student relation is the foundation for determining the professional expertise of the teacher but regrettably most teachers and teacher education institutions are in the dark about its fundamentals in quality human capital development upon which the national development of states depend. Using the philosophical methodology and guided by self-determination theory and social constructivism, this study exclusively focuses on creating creative insights on the fundamentals of teacher student relationship in the classroom and educational institution. The paper recommends innovative directions through which teacher student relationship can be promoted in educational institutions, part of which is that teacher education institutions should introduce courses that can focus on developing in would- be teachers the skills for the promotion of habits that are supportive of cordial relationship between teachers and learners, teachers and students should develop capacity for building trust, self-confidence, self-discipline and care and educational institutions should create enabling environments that can be supportive of teacher student relationship among other recommendations

Keywords: development, human capital, learning, teacher- student relationship

INTRODUCTION

Every state that is desirous of social, moral, economic, political, scientific, technological and general development or advancement prioritizes quality investments in its citizens or more technically makes human capital development the focus of its policies and programmes. Investments in human capital as the rallying point for development derive impetus and justification from the premise that human beings are the carriers of the genes that form and transform into development. This, in all honesty is a polite reminder that no development of any configuration can take place or manifest without the efforts of human beings and in the same way as human beings are the vectors and carriers of the genes of development, so are human beings the vectors and carriers of the genes of underdevelopment or stagnation.

From ages, humanity has recognized that the consciousness for investments in human beings is one of the sure foundations or routes for the continuity and sustenance of life on earth and this awareness is deep rooted in man's recognition that progress and transition from one level of growth and development to the other is a constant variable in the affairs of man, but however, this awareness is equally counter-balanced by the fact that progress and transition in the affairs of man do not naturally and automatically occur without such progress and transition being triggered and stimulated by forces in the environment notably man. This simply implies that the desire for social, moral, economic, political, scientific, technological and general developments must consciously be stimulated or triggered by forces in the environment of man. One major institution and social provision through which humanity generally or states that hold investments in human capital development in high esteem or high regard can rely on or can use in actualizing the noble and lofty ambition of sustainable progress and transition from one level of growth and development to the other in the affairs of man is education.

Scholars have taken cognizance of the fact that education is one social service whose provisions has potentials to qualitatively translate into quality and superlative formations, reformations and transformations of the society and scholars have equally noted that responsible states make its provision a top most priority among the social services that states make available for their citizens (Shively, 2005). There are many other reasons why responsible states epically and phenomenally focus on providing education. Education is the foundation for the formation, reformation, and transformation of the people and their state from one level of development to the other. Through education, states structurally provide roadmaps and blueprints for the development of the people and the state. Put slightly different, stakeholders in a state usually rely on education for systematically charting or developing long range plans that specifically address the provision of education along areas of need that are critical for the development of the people and their state. This means that education serves as a guiding compass for conditioning the impressionable minds of the young into directions that the state and its leaders deem appropriate. Relying on education, the state develops the critical and creative capacities of the citizens in directions where consciousness for nationalism and patriotism for one's father land becomes a topmost priority and citizens of a state who receive education along these lines demonstrate broader outlooks in terms of demonstrating abilities for developing new lens for understanding phenomena and interpreting local and international issues. These attributes, which education develops in the citizens of a state account for why Fagalind and Saha (1989: 100) write that education broadens respectively and mental horizon, instills new values and beliefs that are supportive of modernization programmes and goals and promotes national unity and identity.

States whose citizens receive education to a certain threshold have been critically and intellectually empowered so much that they can contribute to the smooth running of the state as they can conveniently participate in promoting and sustaining justice, social justice, human rights, democracy and democratic principles or norms of the state as well as other norms that aim at supporting social stability and empowerment for the citizens of the state. This, by extension means that states that have prioritized the provision of education for their citizens have consciously and systematically secure a robust and promising future for such citizens as such citizens are not likely to face the hazards of job scarcity or unemployment rather can according to Aminigo and Nwaokugha (2010:50), become more productive and easier to govern but difficult to enslave and colonize. In fact, these point in directions that education provides man with all the basic critical and emancipating thoughts for advancement, inculcates in man the curiosity to master, conquer, explore and exploit the resources of nature for his development.

These emancipating, liberating and empowering potentials of education make the quest, attainment and the pursuit of education unquenchable so much that in addition to states using it for translating their policies and programmes into reality, parents according to Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:433), consider themselves as monumental, epical and phenomenal failures when they fail to provide education for their sons, daughters and wards, a commitment that commits them into going extra miles to ensure that they provide quality education for their sons, daughters and wards. It is obvious and certain that one moral principle that guides the attitudes of parents and the state towards education is that the provision of education for the citizens is a fundamental human rights of citizens. Scholars are favourably disposed to

education as a human right and have equally favourably highlighted the rootedness of the provision of education in human rights discourse. According to Nwaokugha (2015:70), education as a human right connotes an aura of sacredness which confers the provision of education to citizens as a fundamental natural right, which no one ought to be denied of. A detailed justification why education is a human right is provided by Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:433), in these words:

It has to be said and said very unambiguously that the claim that education is a human right is deeply rooted in the fact that its provision at least to a certain threshold for the citizens can serve as a springboard and foundation that has potential to empower citizens in any endeavor of their choice later in life. The idea of providing intellectual empowerment upon which education as a human right revolves invokes an aura of moral responsibility and moral rationality on parents as well as on the state to provide education for the citizens as a fundamental requirement for the survival of the individual and the sustainable development of the state, a development, which when viewed critically is in the best interest of parents and the state.

Any clinical scrutiny of the intention of the global community in making education a fundamental human right can reveal that such intention may hinge on the premise that anyone who has been provided opportunities for education and has consciously claimed such opportunities and right to education, may have gained knowledge, skills or empowerment or has been provided with sustainable skills with which he can explore, exploit, navigate, adapt or may have been provided creative and critical strategies that can enable him respond to change and manage change in a world and system where change occurs in split seconds and more importantly learn to contribute to his growth, the growth of the society as well as learn to existentially hold himself accountable for all his actions. This suggests that the interests of parents and the state in providing education for the citizens is not in vain or is not neutral. Education across all societies of the world is provided with some predetermined intentions, which according to Eboh (1996:130), is either for domestication or for freedom. Education, according to Eboh (1996), serves as an institution or process for the domestication of a people when education serves as mere instrument for socialization whose essential duty is to preserve the status quo and as a means of attaining freedom when it serves as an eye opener for the awakening of creative and critical consciousness in he who has received it. Associated with education as an institution and a means for the domestication of a people is the inclination to use education solely for producing for the society a band-wagon of yes-members whose actions and senses of responsibility cannot make any meaningful contributions or affect any meaningful change in the society while education serves as a process and institution for opening the eyes of the people when education and its provision is to develop in individuals attributes of critical and creative consciousness, spirit of autonomy, analytic alertness, reflective sensibility and other emancipatory, empowerment and liberating behavioural dispositions where he who has received education existentially takes his own destiny in his own hands through his actions.

The right direction that aligns with freedom, which education should follow is along trajectories where it can become the gateway to progressive development and modernization, key for discovering opportunities and what Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:434) call beacon of hope for challenging structural injustices, structural inequalities, poverty, marginalization, deprivation and many other forms of behaviours that are anti-thetical to genuine human capital development, human capital building and national development. In the human capital and general development missions of education, there are many critical stakeholders whose individual and collective contributions and efforts are the litmus and window through which education illuminates its transformative and reformative potentials. Two of such major stakeholders in educational institutions stand out and they are the teacher and the student.

The teacher is fundamentally and foundationally critical in being at the centre between all the other critical stakeholders in education as he is responsible for translating policies and programme decisions into reality and his ability and capacity in doing this is usually at its best when the teacher is positively disposed to demonstrating the highest forms of commitments and devotion to his duties, and part of what can stimulate or motivate the teacher into showing such exceptional commitment and devotion can be the extent in which his employer meets up his obligations such as providing incentives or not found wanting

in issues that border on motivation-salaries, leave bonuses and good working environment. The attitude of the teacher to his duty can be lukewarm when he is owed months of salaries, when there is excess workload, when he works with dictatorial, autocratic and authoritarian head teacher. As a critical stakeholder, the student serves as the index for ascertaining the extent in which education policies, programmes and all the ideals of education translate into reality especially in terms of the ability and capacity of education to bring about changes, reforms and transformations. In fact, the student is the principal agent of change, reform and transformation and correspondingly is the focus of all the entire new narratives, empowerment and emancipation expected of education and on the basis of this, the interest and welfare of the student is usually of paramount concern. Globally, educational institutions prioritize the interest and the welfare of the student through providing state of the art infrastructure and conducive environment for teaching and learning that can provide security and comfort for the student.

However, a worrisome trend and a cause for concern is that not many persons are aware that despite meeting incentive, welfare and motivation needs of teachers and despite guaranteeing the comfort and security needs of students in terms of providing state of the art learning infrastructure for students that can enhance their maximum academic achievement, students in educational institutions still perform and achieve below expectations. What had been said above can be restated that there are moments and instances where all the motivational needs of the teacher and the student can be provided yet the teacher and the student in educational institutions fall far behind the level of academic achievement expected from them by parents, the state and the general public, a development that significantly points in the direction that there is a missing gap. True, when there is a missing gap between the teacher and the student in educational institutions, all efforts at promoting academic achievement fail. The missing gap in educational institutions that defies and neutralizes the motivating power of the availability of superlative infrastructure, the availability of qualified personnel and the availability of students whose socio-economic backgrounds can be added advantages yet expected academic achievements are far behind is the absence of teacher-student relationship.

True, holistic teaching and learning and holistic attainment of the objectives of education in any society or state and their concomitant reformation and transformation of the learner (student) and the state generally strongly depends on the degree of morality driven or motivated relationships that exist among the stakeholders in education. No doubt, teaching and learning in all ramifications is a relational social service that is one hundred percent dependent on networks of relationships between student and student, teacher and parents, school and parents, school and community and school and the state. In these networks of relationships, the relationship that exists between the teacher and the student is so foundational, so focal, topical and so central so much that consolidating, sustaining and maintaining it is a recipe for achieving all the dividends that are associated with the social investment in human capital development of the state.

Effective teacher-student relationship is key to any meaningful achievement in teaching and learning in particular and in education generally and is necessary and fundamental for both the teachers' and the students' level of productivity. Scholars recognize that teacher-student relationship promises many dividends ranging from higher academic achievement and sense of belonging (Jones & Nillas, 2022), serving as a fundamental requirement for understanding student engagement (Pianta, Hamre & Allen, 2012), to being a reliable, dependable and powerful tool in the hand of teachers for fostering and promoting favourable learning environment. According to Rahmayani and Eliasa (2024), a positive relationship between teachers and students can increase students' motivation to learn and their involvement in the learning process. We can add that where positive teacher-student relationship exists, it can become a springboard upon which students can leverage upon especially by exploring and exploiting the social status of their teachers as influencers, motivators and role models to modify, reform and transform their character for their personal good and the good of the state as a whole.

Teacher-student relationship has in-built dynamic mechanisms that can help to professionally improve the productivity and efficiency levels of the teacher and the student as leveraging on it can help the teacher to articulate and develop capacity to professionally acquire skills for addressing the needs of the student through fashioning out and designing instructional innovations and strategies that can work best at any

particular point in time. Teacher-student relationship has potentials to stimulate in the teacher a forward looking, optimistic, enthusiastic outlook and worldview, where the teacher develops a robust sense of joy, a robust sense of fulfilment, a sense of accomplishment and self-efficacy, all deriving from the teachers' participation in recreating his environment and participating in co-creation, a development that singularly and in combination increases the level of motivation, devotion and commitment of the teacher. Teacher-student relationship is instrumental in positively influencing both the teacher and the student in directions where they become more morally and ethically conscious so much that they learn to structure and pattern their behaviours to align with socially acceptable ways of the society with an underlying aim of each becoming more responsible and accountable. In fact, the remark by Rahmayani and Eliasa (2024) summarizes the inherent potentials of teacher-student relationship when they write that "a good teacher-student relationship is key to creating an effective learning environment and supporting the overall development of the student. Emotional involvement, academic support and the role of the teachers as role models are essential in building these relationships"

On the other hand, it is as obvious as day and night that any compromise or attempts at not prioritizing teacher-student relationship in teaching and learning that is fundamentally and foundationally a relational endeavour can be a disaster in a people's conscious quest for human capital development. It is true that undermining teacher-student relationship is responsible for the epical and phenomenal increase in cases of burnout, stress, frustration, general disenchantment with teaching, fatigue and lack of job satisfaction among teachers, a development that has been at the heart and centre of many people leaving the teaching profession and the unfortunate and subsequent flooding of quacks into the teaching profession, who do not have any meaningful thing to contribute to the noble profession of teaching. Again, it has also been established that poor teacher-student relationship is the cause of the global deteriorating student discipline in educational institutions (Kasivu, 2020:319).

Deriving from the above expositions, a million dollars question is: to what extent do teachers, students, parents, teacher education institutions and other critical stakeholders in education recognize that teacher-student relationship is so foundational and fundamental in human capital development of states that is realized through teaching and learning in particular and education in general? An answer to the question above is simple: stakeholders in education hardly know the essentials of teacher-student relationship. This ignorance is regrettable and is a serious gap that needs to be addressed. This study is therefore motivated by the researchers' interests to create awareness and insights on the essentials of teacher-student relationship especially in mankind's quest for human capital development.

This study on the essentials of teacher-student relationship in human capital development can be specially relevant to the teacher, student, parents, teacher education institutions, the government and non-governmental organizations among other beneficiaries. This study can create new consciousness in teachers that outside formal qualifications, the disposition to initiate relationships that are deep rooted in humanism and sound morality with the students can be key to achieving all the reformative and transformative potentials of education in the quest of any state for human capital development. The implication here is that this study can reshape and restructure the personality of the teacher into acknowledging that what a student can remember as having made the most indelible impression in him may not be the teaching in class but the influence of the teacher over the student, which only teacher-student relationship can establish. This study can sensitize the student that creating and sustaining a good teacher-student relationship is like acquiring a compass with which to navigate the ever-complex human society as the student who keeps such teacher student relationship can robustly benefit from the accumulated experiences of the teacher, which naturally must exert some influence on the student. It follows logically that this study can provide the student with explorable existential lens on direction to take and who to focus his impressionable mind on for possible lines of actions that can shape, enhance and influence his academic pursuits. In this way, this study can create insights and awareness for the student on the choice of who can be his role model or influencer in life and this decision can enhance his academic progress and achievement. The result of this study can be of immense benefit to parents as well initiated and well explored teacher-student relationship can result in better moral upbringing of the student through the students' demonstration of mature and sophisticated behavioural disposition and such

mature and sophisticated moral display can be such that can influence parents or parents can learn from. Again, the influence from such teacher-student relationship can boost parents' investments in the students as well as raise parents' level of joy, happiness, fascination, enthusiasm, and love for the students.

Teacher education institutions can immensely benefit from the result of this study as the study can challenge them into structurally and epistemologically developing innovations and pedagogical theorizing for the education of would-be teachers and re-education of those already in service, where the new focus can be on the incorporation of courses that can exclusively focus on skills and techniques for promoting and sustaining teacher-student relationship. In fact, this study can trigger a revolution in teacher education that targets expanding and revolutionizing teacher education so that it can jettison or repudiate its excessive conservatism on one hand and initiate actions that can align it with current realities in human capital development in the twenty first century on the other. The government whose responsibility it is to consciously raise stronger human capital base for the development of the state can find this study relevant through exploring and translating the new pedagogical, policy and new narratives canvassed by the study into reality. The study can stimulate beneficial guides and insights, which the government can use to influence policies and programmes across the length and breadth of teacher education programmes in particular and education generally and lastly non-governmental organizations who show capacity and interests in human capital development can benefit from this study in its context specific relationship strategies, which non-governmental organizations can exploit in their human capital development initiative across the globe.

The theoretical frameworks upon which this study is based are self-determination theory and social constructivism. Self-determination theory is a multidimensional human development theory that attracts a lot of attention from scholars and correspondingly scholars express different but related viewpoints about it. According to Reeve (2012), self-determination theory is a macro-theory of motivation that is comprised of five inter-related mini-theories – basic need theory, organismic theory, integrated theory, cognitive evaluation theory and causality evaluation theory.

Self-determination theory is a human development theory that is inherently deep rooted in the roles of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in enhancing and promoting the growth and development of the individual. Unique to this theory is the recognition that the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations of the individual cannot and does not on their own translate into reality rather such intrinsic and extrinsic motivations according to Ryan and Deci (2020) must require the guidance and support of someone else for their manifestations to be robust, effective and meaningful. What is at the heart of self-determination theory is that self-determination of the individual is the foundational and fundamental force that propels the wheel of motivation and the individual who is self-determined explores his state of mind through a demonstration of a sense of self control, initiation of ideas and a capacity to make autonomous choices.

Ryan and Deci (2020) write that for whatever intrinsic and extrinsic motivations anyone has to meaningfully and effectively translate into reality; there are three foundational and fundamental conditions that the individual who manifests such intrinsic and extrinsic motivations must have. The three conditions are; autonomy, competence and relatedness. Autonomy, when mentioned in discussions that are focused on self-determination theory invokes a meaning that revolves around the fact that individuals who are desirous of growth and development can match same ambition with manifestations of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, in the form of equally demonstrating a sense of autonomous ownership of such ideas and initiatives and be capable of practically and theoretically translating such ideas into actions. It follows that the idea of autonomy points to the self and demands the self to be self-determined. What is expected of the individual is hinted at by Brooks and Young (2011:49), when they write that “to be self-determined means self-propelled to act and thus having agency in one’s own performance”.

Competence as it concerns self-determination theory demands from the individual who is desirous of growth and development to show capacity in the form of show of expertise in the mastery of certain skills through which the individual can translate his intrinsic and extrinsic motivations into reality. Relatedness as a term in discussions that are focused on self-determination theory of human development and motivation makes a case that the individual who is desirous and curious of development should correspond such ambition with a sense of belonging, creativity, critical thinking and connections,

including the desire to care for others and to be cared for by others. What is at the centre of relatedness in discussion of self-determination and human development theory is the ability of the individual to be socially connected (Brooks and Young, 2011:49). From whichever perspective scholars handle the theory, one common denominator that all the three above shares in common is that they are all focused on the phenomenon of motivation and how this can be explored or manipulated in the course of providing students pedagogical instructions so that high quality and superlative student engagement that can lead to higher achievement can be achieved.

As a theoretical framework for the establishment of knowledge, social constructivism maintains that knowledge of all configurations owes their roots to human ingenuity, human creative insights, human creativity and human critical consciousness and a revelation which this expose is that human beings are the architects, constructors and builders (Nwaokugha & Odinka, 2025, Nwaokugha, 2025 and Nwaokugha & Moses, 2025) of whatever knowledge that exists. It can equally be stated that this theory of knowledge construction holistically holds the various experiences of man and the various ways in which man interacts with his environment to be the trajectories through which knowledge evolves. The above aligns very well with the position maintained by Liu and Matthew (2005:357), who specifically write that “knowledge is not mechanically acquired but constructed with the constraints and offerings of the learning environment”. That the instrumentality of man, his experience and environment in knowledge construction aligns with the lens of social constructivism is forcefully spotlighted by Nwaokugha (2025:24) when he writes that:

What is at the heart or centre of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is the awareness that no knowledge of any configuration is ready made and correspondingly sampled or displayed anywhere to be purchased or hired by who wants it, rather knowledge of any configuration can be produced, generated and constructed through the conscious, critical and creative efforts of an individual or individuals who demonstrate creative engagement, commitment and critical consciousness in the search for knowledge.

The emphasis that man is the architect, constructor and builder of knowledge is a pointer that knowledge construction is a development that does not occur by chance rather the individual or individuals who are keen on generating or constructing knowledge must show some level of readiness, preparedness and curiosity especially in their attitude and behavioural dispositions. An appropriate behavioural disposition or attitude that anyone who is interested and keen on constructing knowledge under the frame of reference of social constructivism is one where the individual can actively commit himself to creating and recreating insights that target breaking new frontiers that can become a beacon of hope in solving problems, drive and initiate change and such agent of change must be willing to collaborate and cooperate with other people who share similar dreams or visions and most importantly must be willing and ready to make creative and critical thinking norms in his daily affairs.

Self-determination theory and social constructivism as the theoretical frameworks upon which this study is based are considered appropriate and suitable for the study. The appropriateness of self-determination theory for this study lies in the centrality of the theory to acknowledge the role of relationship, precisely the role of another individual in shaping, sharpening, guiding, directing and strengthening the intrinsic and extrinsic motivations of another person, possibly a learner, a development that lays formidable foundations for favourable attitudinal dispositions that can be supportive of epistemological revolutions especially the deepening of critical and creative insights that can strategically and intellectually empower the learner and the teacher into developing confidence in themselves that can enhance their abilities to improve on the academic ladder for growth and higher academic achievements. In fact, it must be emphasized that the boosting of the confidence level of the teacher and the learner repositions these two critical stakeholders in education for mutual benefits in the form of greater productivity that can translate into better professional development for the teacher, higher academic achievement for the learner and sustainable national development for the state.

On the other hand, the relevance of social constructivism for this study lies in its ability to create awareness and sensitize humanity that the skills, growth, production and advancement of knowledge do not owe their roots to any mechanical permutation or formula rather they are the creation of man that

can be possible if and only if man continuously interacts with his environment, explores, creates and recreates his experiences in his environment, including demonstrating a high level of curiosity, critical and creative consciousness towards mastering, explaining and interpreting phenomena in his environment. What this points hand to is the promotion of attitudinal disposition where the individual recognizes that he is a critical stakeholder in the business of knowledge production and takes it that part of his responsibility to mankind is the task of continuously expanding the frontiers of knowledge. It can be correct that part of the legacy of this theory is its insights on sensitizing and conscientizing humanity not to allow the flame of knowledge to go into extinction.

Interestingly, there is a thin line that unites and brings the two theories used in this study together and that is that the two theories are highly sensitive on issues that border on motivation, human capital development and qualitative growth of knowledge. That the focus of the two theories used as theoretical background of this study are on the above means that the two theories are appropriate for this study on teacher-student relationship, which directly and indirectly have implications for quality human capital development.

One inherent feature which studies whose theoretical frameworks are hinged on self-determination and social constructivism share in common is the alignment of such with the qualitative or philosophical research design or methodology and this accounts for the reason why qualitative or philosophical research methodology is the methodology for this study. Qualitative or philosophical research methodology is specially unique and its uniqueness has epically and phenomenally positioned it for attention among scholars and researchers. According to Angadi (2019:39), one feature that qualitative or philosophical research methodology is known for is its ability to robustly and monumentally rely on the collection of extensive narrative data on many variables over extended period of time in a naturalistic setting to gain insights not possible using other types of research methods. The inclination of qualitative or philosophical research methodology to rely on the collection of extensive narrative data can be said to be the strength and powerhouse of this type of research methodology. This position can be said to derive justification from the observation made by Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159) that qualitative or philosophical research methodology offers scholars and researchers who are receptive to using it sufficient freedom to freely express and communicate their ideas to humanity on both specific and general issues. A revelation which this expose is that the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is interested in constantly and repeatedly breaking epistemological frontiers and through this way keep the flames of knowledge and human development burning. This curiosity for repeatedly breaking epistemological frontiers of knowledge and through this way skyrocket human and national development is deep rooted in an epistemological tradition where epical and phenomenal analytic scrutiny, rigours of thought, semantic clarity and logical coherence are norm that are used for the establishment of knowledge.

The preoccupation of qualitative or philosophical research with the above enables it to incorporate interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross-disciplinary academic expeditions across disciplines. Part of what may account for the reason why qualitative or philosophical research methodology preoccupies itself with all the above can be its focus on creating insights on what had happened in the past, what is happening in the present and what may happen in the future with a view to discussing, highlighting, pointing out and predicting possible implications and possible new developments that may likely become norms following such experiences. The ability of qualitative or philosophical researches or studies to create insight is highlighted by Ishtiaq and Naz (2024:10) in these words:

Qualitative research is exploratory, aiming to uncover new insights, perspectives and understanding within educational settings. Qualitative research in education involves collecting and analysing non-numerical data such as interviews, observation, case studies, and document analysis. The aim is to generate in-depth insights, explore meanings and understand the underlying processes that shape educational phenomena

The widespread acceptance of qualitative or philosophical research methodology by scholars and researchers across disciplines is anchored on the fact that qualitative or philosophical research methodology incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription (Nwaokugha & Dandali, 2016). According to Nwaokugha and Smith-Ogizeh (2025:159) speculation as a qualitative or philosophical

research methodology is not a new comer in the world of knowledge and the basis upon which such a conclusion has been reached can be the fact that ancient philosophers who made indelible impressions in the world of knowledge and whose positions still dominate and still remain influential in the world of knowledge today heavily relied on speculation. It is a fact that cannot be doubted that scholars and researchers who made earliest attempts at the development and construction of knowledge acknowledged speculation to be the fundamental and foundational pillars for successful practice in science (Currie, 2021) and other disciplines, a revelation which Gire (2020) acknowledges when he admits that speculation is primordial to all experiences and thinking. In what can be taken as an acknowledgement of the above, Nwaokugha and Smitt-Ogizeh (2025:154) write that speculation can be applied in philosophy and its applied disciplines, social sciences and natural sciences and what can be as clear as day and night in discussions that revolve around speculation is the fact that its meaning keeps shifting and admitting specific semantic colourations in the different contexts in which it is mentioned. Definitions of speculation as provided by scholars and researchers attest to this. Speculation according to Oduor (2010:97) is to wonder, conjecture, guess and to hypothesize while Haung, Xie and Chen (2021) write that speculation or speculative thinking is that type of thinking about past and future possibilities, which includes counter-factual thinking, pre-factual thinking and other types of thinking. To Aminigo (1999) and Agulana (2011), speculation is any consciously initiated attempts to find logical coherence in an entire realm of thought while Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:4) write that speculation invokes a meaning that revolves around a sense of logical unity, logical coherence and logical clarity about a presentation that is the subject matter of a philosophical discourse. In an attempt to shed more light on the meaning of speculation, Swedberg (2021) provides a two-way definition of speculation. According to him, speculation is associated with two meanings namely:

1. A risky but potentially very profitable economic activity, and
2. The making of conjectures without firm evidence

It can be said with absolute certainty and assurance that speculation and speculative thinking transitions on trajectories where the normal order of events is one where a conclusion derives from the premise before it or more technically that the reasonability, acceptability, semantic soundness, logical appropriateness, authenticity, truthfulness and originality of a claim, presentation or argument can only be established on one condition namely when a conclusion reached at the end of a presentation or argument logically and rationally derives from the premise before it, then the claim, proposition or argument can be said to be correct and valid.

Speculation and speculative thinking makes meaningful and sustainable impacts and will continue to make meaningful impacts on the lives of scholars and researchers as well as influence and restructure reformations and transformations in the society and the world of knowledge across the world. This observation can be said to be deep rooted in the fact that speculation and speculative thinking triggers and develops in man robust curiosity and initiate drives that are supportive of quality change, quality innovations and a consciousness for the re-evaluation of prevailing practices in the society with a view to initiating behavioural revolutions that can add value to the quality of life of the members of the society or more precisely make positive change a norm in the affairs of a state. It is in the spirit of the foregoing that Taggart (2021) writes that speculation and speculative thinking is synonymous with providing man and his institutions new critical, creative and evaluative lens that trigger and pop up in man a philosophy that can lead to the formulation of actions and policies for building and sustaining a public philosophy or individual and collective philosophy of life that can serve as a model for individuals, the society and the state at large. Any analytic insight on the above can point in the direction that speculation and speculative thinking is a capstone for reengineering new directions in thinking and is particularly resorted to when prevailing way of thinking or old ways of doing things can no longer provide sustainable and satisfactory remedies and solutions to present and contemporary challenges and problems of man and the state. This is where scholars who recognize that speculation and speculative thinking are epistemological navigating compass in the affairs of man and his institutions (Nwaokugha & Nwaogu, 2024:63) as well as foundations that serve as a springboard, a trigger and a provocateur of actions can be said to be one hundred percent correct. In fact, Nwaokugha (2025:26) says it all when writes that:

Speculation is synonymous with promoting curious behavioural dispositions that are supportive of conscious drives that target providing new guidance, innovation, transformation, new ways of doing things or re-examination of practices with a view to overcoming and transcending to higher levels so that quality improvement may be introduced into the practices of man and his institutions.

To this end, it can be said and said very strongly that speculation easily becomes the next strategy for survival, the next direction to look toward and a practice to embrace for translating human actions into sustainable reality especially when man is in dire need to know, when man is seriously desirous of formation, reformation and transformation from his present state of affairs that may have lost its value, depreciated and consequently no more relevant in the face of prevailing circumstances and realities. Anyone who carefully examines the above can come to the conclusion that the seal of change is inherent on speculation and correspondingly those disciplines according to Nwaokugha and Moses (2025:439) that are more receptive to change and do not have universal or a one-size-fits-all answers to questions they pose or generate are most attractive to speculation. To this end, topics that have their roots or sphere of influence in metaphysics and axiology are best handled speculatively.

As obvious as this can be, it is important we point out that metaphysical and axiological topics allow the phenomenon and direction of change to prevail on them and what this translate into is that a scholar or a researcher can change, modify or out-rightly take a new position that may be different from the one he had already taken before and that someone had already taken a position on a metaphysical and axiological topic does not stop another scholar or researcher from taking his own position. In all of these, the prevailing circumstances surrounding a metaphysical or an axiological subject matter at its most current or latest time of discussion can be the determining factor that can determine what can be said about such metaphysical and axiological subject matter. Language and logic are important instruments in effective, impactful and meaningful speculation.

Historical antecedents on the origin of analysis as a method of qualitative or philosophical research methodology can be traced to ancient philosophers such as Socrates, Plato, Aristotle etc (Nwaokugha & Moses, 2025:439) and correspondingly analysis as a methodology of qualitative or philosophical studies or research is not a new comer in man's quest to develop, construct or build knowledge as right from the inception of the world, there has been conscious efforts by man to explicitly make meaning and to understand himself and his environment. Such conscious efforts of man to make meaning explicit, to understand himself and others as well as his environment fall within the frame of reference of analysis. Practically, analysis concerns itself with the critical examination of words, terms, concepts and propositions with a view to making explicit the meanings that may be associated with such words, terms, concepts, and propositions. Inherent in analysis is a higher sensitivity to logical clarity, semantic and linguistic precision so that issues of absurdities, meaninglessness, contradictions, and ambiguities that may be located in the meanings of words, terms, concepts, and propositions, can be addressed or located and attention maybe fixed on any particular meaning that may be the focus of the use of a term or concept in any particular discussion. To this end, analysis is undertaken to enhance and promote effective communication, clarification, cooperation, and better human relationships.

It has been noted by scholars and researchers that analysis has become the trending practice and the destination of choice for individuals and institutions who are desirous of making quality contributions to the world of knowledge, and this development may have accounted for why Nwaokugha (2025:27) writes that the extraordinary

Focus of analysis on the clarification of meaning is deep-rooted in the fact that virtually all crises, conflicts, misunderstandings, disagreements, and wars that have wreaked havoc on man and his institutions across the globe are traceable to faulty use of words, terms, concepts, and propositions or faulty communication or miscommunication.

This implies that promoting the skills of analysis in man and his institutions or making analysis a norm in man's daily activities should be receptively supported to the point of making it an area of serious concern in human affairs. In fact, analysis as a critical and reflective practice has potentials for promoting peace and social harmony, and in any environment, institution or state where analysis is the prevailing norm or

practice, it has the practical benefit of skyrocketing the intellectual sophistication of those who practice it as well as helps to minimize confusion and crisis in the affairs of man and his institutions, (Nwaokugha & Wogonwu,2020). In fact, analysis has potentials to radicalize and revolutionize the world of knowledge, including serving as a springboard for improving the quality of human relations upon which the national development of states depends (Nwaokugha & Rotimi-Aina, 2025). The above expositions can be suggesting that analysis has potentials to extend and expand the frontiers, constituencies, and boundaries of knowledge, build foundations for peace and harmonious coexistence, and can be a recipe for human capital or human capacity development of a state. When this happens, analysis can be said to be creating more emancipating and more empowering opportunities for man in the form of adding value to the quality of life of man and the operational space of his institutions.

Analysts do their critical and reflective work of analysis by breaking down their subject matter into smaller units that constitute the whole and point out likely meanings and specific contexts that each unit may be associated with. In fact, analysts in most cases call attention to specific contexts in which meaning of a term, word or concept so far analyzed can apply. Analysis is of two types, namely conceptual and linguistic analysis. Conceptual analysis focuses on establishing if the meaning that is associated with a concept is actually what the concept stands for, while linguistic analysis focuses on ascertaining if the meaning that is ascribed to a sentence is really what the sentence represents.

Every study that is worth the name must focus on solving or addressing at least one specific problem and attempt at doing this may discuss many variables that are specifically or generally related to the topic under investigation. The section of any study that focuses on proffering solutions or that recommends ideas on how issues raised or discussed in any scholarly discourse can be resolved reflect meanings that are captured within the frame of reference of prescription. Descriptively, it is always at the last segment of any study where scholars and researchers focus exclusive attention in the form of suggesting and recommending workable strategies for addressing, solving, and resolving identified problems (Nwaokugha & Smith- Ogizeh, 2025). This accounts for why Oduor (2010:97), notes that to prescribe is to recommend and set down as “rule or guide” and Nwaokugha (2021:102) summarizes the foregoing when he writes that prescription:

Is achieved in research in the form of a researcher making autonomous value statements on how an issue that has been the focus or subject matter of a philosophical discussion can be solved so that all the wrongs noticed in the course of the discussion can be harmoniously addressed.

True, prescription is fundamental and critical in every study, as scholars and researchers do not joke with it. However, there are scholars and disciplines that prescription is their powerhouse, article of faith, and heartbeat of what such scholars and disciplines do. Those scholars and disciplines that show interest in axiology-aesthetics, social philosophy, ethics, and political philosophy must prescribe in order to be relevant and impactful in the society, and the directions of what such scholars and disciplines prescribe are guided by the phenomenon of change, which according to Nwaokuga and Odinka, (2025:183) must consistently dictate, influence and determine the rhythm of the action of man and his institutions.

The use of the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is appropriate for this study. It is self-evident that all aspects of knowledge benefit from philosophical reflections and creative insights that are inherent in philosophical or qualitative studies. Therefore, the use of this methodology can boost researchers' curiosity and investigative skills, a development that has potential to trigger the breaking of groundbreaking breakthroughs that can challenge scholars and researchers into focusing their studies on terrains and environments that may ordinarily remain unimaginable, un-contemplatable, and unthinkable. That the above is the case means that qualitative or philosophical research methodology has potentials to add value to individual and national development of states. The methodology is supportive of interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary, and cross-disciplinary collaborations and intellectual empowerment of researchers and scholars across disciplines among other benefits of qualitative or philosophical research methods. Any study or research that the scholar or researcher employs the qualitative or philosophical research methodology is known for one feature and that feature is detailed or exclusive focus on key concept(s) in the study and to this we now turn.

The Teacher

It is true and correct that the school or the education industry is one social institution that performs many roles and responsibilities for humanity. Humanity looks up to the school or educational institutions for directions, guidance, reforms, humane radical initiatives, and revolutionary transformations for taking man and his institutions to the next levels, especially the acquisition of skills for sustainable exploration of the resources of the environment. The school or the education industry is specially and uniquely structured to meet up these roles and responsibilities for the individual persons and institutions that make up the society, particularly when individuals and institutions of the society do not share the same values and the same characteristics. Virtually all human beings and the institutions of the society that look up to education for guidance and direction do not like or dislike the same value or do not value things of this world in the same way, yet the school or education industry comfortably and satisfactorily provides for the need of every one of them. Because the school or the education industry is one social institution that meets all the needs and demands of every individual person and institution in the society without any trace of failure and compromise, the school or the education industry has become a place where everyone wants to be, a place that identifies the individual with status symbol of modernity and civility, where the focus is on reforms and transformations in positive directions and a social institution and a social provision upon which public deliberations are focused upon, so visible that it is at the centre of politics, especially a means of translating social justice, equality, emancipation, and empowerment into reality. The man who makes all these possible and who is at the center of what happens in the school or the education industry and in fact, who is responsible for all success stories of the school or the education industry is the teacher.

Scholars and researchers hold different but related views about the teacher or whom the teacher is. Suryani (2018:263) identifies a teacher as a person who works in an educational institute or institution to help students acquire knowledge, competence, and values while Ganguly (2022:863) writes that a teacher or formerly an educator is a person who helps students to acquire knowledge, competence, or virtue. What can be taken as a truth that cannot be doubted in discussions that border on the teacher is that he is a professionally educated person in the science and art of pedagogy and their practical applications, and who is specially educated to demonstrate expertise in knowledge construction, knowledge generation, knowledge dissemination, human capital development, and national development of states. In pragmatic and functional terms, the teacher is a key personality, a resource person, a critical personnel and an asset in whatever that happens in the school or the education industry so important that most modern states, across the world capture and emphasize in their national development policies and national policy on education that no education system, and by implication, no measure and policy of any state that is focused on human capital development or national development of any state can rise above the quality of teachers who administer or manage the school or the education industry.

In fact, Suryani (2018:263) says it all when he writes that the most important element in the learning process is a teacher. Therefore, the teacher is the most significant and the most influential figure in the life of every student. The above observation points at the importance of the teacher as success in teaching and learning that are critical functions of the school or the education industry, which also doubles as a critical foundation for the development of the state in particular and humanity generally depends on him-the teacher. To this end, the teacher functions at multiple levels, such as a role model, a nation builder, a character molder, a motivator, a bridge builder between learners, parents, and the government, serves as one who is entrusted with the responsibility of implementing state policies on education, a guidance counsellor, and one entrusted with realizing all the values that are associated with education. Apart from the above, the teacher teaches learners in the school, interacts with learners in the school, cares for learners in the school, mentors learners in and outside the school, influences and shapes the values and visions of the learners beyond the school, assesses learners in the school, and such assessments become the basis for placing learners on job trajectories as well as foundations for their social and occupational mobility in the larger society. The teacher is also a social influencer, a mobiliser, and a community development expert.

The foregoing points to the fact that the role of the teacher is polymorphous, multifaceted, complex, fluid, and more importantly, very sensitive and responsive to the whims and caprices of the prevailing circumstances as dictated by change, especially along trajectories that align with the current happenings, innovations, reforms, and transformations that identify with the trending needs of the members of the society. In fact, the influence of the teacher is so phenomenal and impactful across all layers of the society so much that his actions in the communities account for a reasonable percentage of visible developments and advancements of humanity. A summary of the critical roles of the teacher in the effective functioning of the school has been provided by Nwaokugha (2014:15) in these words:

The teacher is so fundamental that he is at the centre of all reforms and innovations in education to the point that “perfect” educational policies and programmes with corresponding financial backings can translate to nothing if teachers who are the implementers and drivers of the policies in the education industry are not in adequate supply, committed and dedicated. The upshot of the above is that teachers are responsible for translating and actualizing educational policies and programs into actions.

We must point out that the focus of the teacher is to teach learners, disseminate information and construct knowledge and this follows trajectories where what the teacher teaches, the information he disseminates and the knowledge he constructs derives from the subject matter(s) or topic(s) prescribed by the appropriate authorities of the state for an identifiable level of learners for a specified period of time. This means what the teacher teaches the learner, takes into cognizance the age and the class of the learner, and this specification simply means that the teacher cannot on his own and in the name of teaching learners, superimpose on learners whatever knowledge he deems fit. This points in the direction of a robust and vibrant teacher education programme that the teacher must undergo for purposes of acquiring the right content knowledge and pedagogical skills for sharpening his effectiveness and efficiency on the job. The teacher education programme also equips the teacher with the capacity to develop emotional, social and psychological skills especially the ability to build trusting, long lasting and compassionate relationships with learners and possession of knowledge and understanding of learners and variables that can enhance or hinder learning. The above sharpens and skyrockets the capacity of teachers to be impactful, and most impactful teachers in the teaching and learning process are those teachers who demonstrate passion, trust, confidence, respect for themselves and learners, sincerity, kindness, empathy, and love for their learners. Where the above prevails, the learners or students reciprocate in many positive ways, especially by cooperating with the teacher in teaching learning process. The attitude of cooperation from the students results in mutual benefits to the teacher and the learner. For the teacher, it leads to more professional growth and inherent inner peace and happiness that emanates from the teacher's belief that the time he invests in teaching students in the school has been fruitful and productive, while for the learners, it leads to greater achievement that shapes and defines opportunities in the future.

The success or otherwise of all the foregoing is dependent on the quality of relationships that exists between the teachers and the learners in the school, for the school, where the teacher and the students are critical stakeholders, are in the words of Goktas and Kuya (2023), institution where human relations are intense. The above has been re-echoed by Suryani (2018:263), when he acknowledges that teachers also play an important role to create classroom climate that relates to teacher and student relationship. In fact, the above scholar is also credited with saying that the role of the teacher does not end with delivering instruction and knowledge to the student, but also that the teacher must build positive relations with the students.

The Student

The school as a social organization is a meeting ground or meeting space for different persons who share different values, who come from different cultures and who belong to different religious denominations as well as different socio-economic and political backgrounds. These different persons who meet or converge in the school also do so for different reasons, purposes or objectives. There are persons who are in the school for the purpose of teaching and researching and there are persons who are in the school for the purposes of learning and mentorship from others. There are other persons whose mission of being in the school (whether public or private school) is to invest and explore the numerous business and

entrepreneurial opportunities that the school as an educational institution can provide and the group that basically comes to mind here is the private investors in education. Whether public or private, the school as a social organization cannot function effectively and efficiently without the participation of the private sector. According to Nwaokugha (2015:75) the private sector provides schools:

Auxiliary social services such as transport for staff and students, catering and maintenance services for staff and students, book publishing and photocopying for staff and students and acting as intermediary between school management and administration and students, contractors and other classes of public institutions recognized vendors in matters of receiving and disbursement of funds.

Of these different groups in the school, there is one in which the soul and heartbeat of the school depend, without which the others cannot exist, that group that is the soul and heartbeat of the school without which the others cannot exist is the student. A student according to Gauguly (2022:863) is primarily a person (who) enrolled in a school or other educational institutions and who is under learning with goals of acquiring knowledge, developing professions and acquiring employment in a desired field. Schools all over the world primarily exist because of students, who are vessels and instruments in the hands of the state for driving development and bringing about social, economic, political, moral, scientific and technological reforms, transformations and revolutions.

The student as a learner in the education industry occupies a critical space in the national development blueprint of states. The student is the focus through which change and transformation of any state can occur, and he is the driving force and instrument for the actualization of whatever visions and aspirations of the leaders of the state. The student fills the gap of whatever innovations, or whatever was not done properly and the means to be use for fixing innovations, whatever failure that past generations could not adequately overcome. What has been said above points in the direction that the hope and aspiration of any state to position or reposition itself along trajectories where its dreams and aspirations to break epistemological and axiological frontiers that can make the state stand tall in comity of states must be routed through the school or the education industry via the student. In reality, the student is at the centre of whatever policy, programme and investment the state makes in education and the student is at the centre of whatever decisions the political class makes for reinventing the state and taking humanity to the next level.

To be a student in a school can be a personal decision and a commitment which an individual can voluntarily make or enter into as a career and existential trajectory that can lead the individual into understanding and defining oneself, can be a pursuit for the accomplishment of a mission or a task, can be a destination where one must be for purpose of actualizing oneself for reasons of developing capacity for influencing issues later in life that can enhance one's contributions to the development of his state and humanity. To be a student can also be the wish of the parents of an individual or the wish of the state as a human right provision for the individual or the wish of the state as a human right provision for the individual, and as a means through which the parent or the state can achieve the future of their dreams or aspirations. What is implicated here is that the parents or the state sends somebody - the student to school as a moral obligation the parent or the state owes himself and the larger society, bearing in mind that the parent or the state cannot fully achieve the dreams of the parent and aspirations of the state that can reflect and represent the trending trends of things all the times. The student here serves as instrument and medium through which all social justice, equality, equity and other moral and inter-generational principles that are supportive of sustainable development, continuous human flourishing and survival of humanity can be actualized. Under this frame of reference, the student serves as a bridge between the present and the future and awareness of this is necessary to challenge particularly the student to be engaged in a critical and rigorous intellectual engagement so as not to disappoint parents, the state and humanity.

It follows that much is expected from the student and equally much is expected from the state to better the plight of the student so as to translate all that is expected from education for humanity into reality. For sure, the student is he whom all the modernizing, moralizing and civilizing ideals of education hovers or revolves around for translation into reality. However, before all these can come to function,

there is one behavioural disposition that can position the student in the forefront of responding and actualizing the great expectations of parents, society, the state and humanity. That expectation is robust and receptive teacher-student relationship.

Teacher-Student Relationship

The school and the education industry is a hotbed of activities and such activities take place mainly in teaching and learning sessions. In every teaching and learning session or process, intentional and unintentional activities occur simultaneously in unpredictable ways and teachers use their professional skills and expertise to address such issues that erupt in the course of teaching and learning. There are some of these that are necessary for effective teaching and learning to take place and a teacher who is professionally conscious of himself causes some of them to occur in the process of teaching and learning. These activities in teaching and learning sessions in particular and in the education industry generally strive on trust, sincerity of purpose, mutual respect, cordiality and harmonious and robust relationships between and among the various critical stake-holders in the education industry. The rootedness of these activities in teaching and learning and education generally on trust, mutual respect, sincerity of purpose, cordiality and harmonious robust relationships have long been acknowledged and this accounts for why scholars and educators recognize that teaching and learning is foundationally and fundamentally a relational activities or a relational endeavour where the ability to cultivate and make relationship a norm determines the degree of productivity, impact and success any one or a group makes in using education to transform the individual and achieve the national objectives of the state. True, relationships between the school and its host community, personnel within the school, education personnel within the field and the government and other corporate institutions in the society are necessary, at least for the exchange of ideas and the building of confidence especially those that can stimulate changes that are capable of making meaningful contributions towards the realization of the objectives and goals of education, but that in the chain of relationships in the education industry that has potentials for the attainment of the general and specific objectives, which education stands for is teacher-student relationship.

Teacher-student relationship in teaching and learning and in the education industry holds the keys for stimulating moral, ethical and positive revolutionary reforms and transformations with potentials for reforming, transforming and actualizing the common dreams of humanity into levels where the learners in particular and the school generally can be better because teacher-student relationship is supportive of positively charging and motivating both the teacher and the learner to greater and higher levels of productivity, teacher-student relationship has been at the fore-front of contemporary discussion among researchers and scholars of education and a follow-up to this has been a phenomenal scholarly attention and focus on teacher-student relation, a development that has resulted to a multiplicity and a plethora of definitions and interpretations.

According to Choristine, Russo, Fitzmorris, Beninato and Rivolta (2022), teacher-student relationship is that type of relationship that exists between a teacher and a student for the sole purpose of the teacher and the student gaining respect from each other. In its own definition of teacher-student relationship, the American Psychological Association (2023) writes that teacher-student relationship is the relationship and interaction that exists between the teacher and the student in a classroom or school setting while Attri (2024) writes that teacher-student relationship is the interaction and bond formed between teachers and students that is characterized by such elements as trust, respect, communication and emotional support. From another perspective, Yan (2019) writes that teacher-student relationship is an aspect of interpersonal relationship between the teacher and the student in the process of teaching and learning that helps us to create a supportive, relaxed, curious, enjoyable and motivation stimulating as well as autonomous individualized learning consciousness in learners that skyrockets, boosts or increases students' level of engagement and academic achievement. In the words of Davis (2003), teacher- student relationship is that type of relationship that exists between the teacher and the student that has low level of conflict and high level of closeness.

Any critical look at the above definitions and interpretations of teacher-student relationship as provided by the above scholars and institution can reveal that teacher-student relationship is a multi-faceted concept whose various definitions and interpretations invokes and revolves around one common denominator:

namely teachers should create and establish cordial and stimulating environments in the school or educational institutions that are supportive and synonymous with norms that are of high moral quality that can make it possible for easy flow of interaction, communication, and relationship between the teachers and students in the school or educational institutions. In other words, what is at the heart of teacher-student relationship is that there should be close and cordial relationship between the teacher and the student in the school and the relationship must be one where the teacher can be approached or reached to the point of students feeling free to relate, communicate and interact with him without any iota of fear or intimidation. In other words, what is at the centre of teacher-student relationship is a multi-faceted application of professional strategies, practices and innovations that are supportive of conducive teaching and learning environment on one hand and robust and excellent human relations practices on the other, where in addition to learning becoming an enjoyable experience and fun, with potentials for reforming and transforming the students, the teacher creates enabling environments that are supportive and conducive for communication, interaction and relationship between him and the student. When sustained this atmosphere of trust, cordiality, respect and confidence so far created by the teacher can produce a behavioural reciprocal equation and balance from the students in the form of the students putting up attitudes of cooperation, becoming friendly and feeling free to express themselves in the classroom and in the school.

Pragmatically, teacher-student relationship strongly derives impetus and justification from the premise that the closer the teacher is to the student and combine and correspond same with the ethics of care, commitment, concern, love, compassion, guidance and empathy, the better he can understand the problems, predicaments, feelings, challenges and difficulties of the students. More than anything else, the students feel important, accepted and respected before any teacher who cares for them. (Al-shraideh, 2017:42)

True, it must be recognized and acknowledged that the school or educational institutions as specialized places for human capital development is synonymous with interactions, communications and relationships at multiple levels that cut across teachers, students, parents, government as well as organizations in the society. However, as obvious as this can be, interaction, communication and relationship between the teacher and the student is more unique as it is most likely to make education more impactful and more productive especially on those indexes for accelerating and promoting the achievement of human capital development and national objectives of states. Thus, it can be said loud and clear that any school or teaching-learning situation where there is a supportive teacher-student relationship, teachers are likely to record astronomical and phenomenal professional growth and development that have potentials to increase their productivity and such can produce a reciprocal effect from students in the form of increased attention, increased engagement, increased achievement, increased trust, increased motivation, increased learning and robust development of self-confidence among the students that can develop into quality development of human capital and quality national development of the state. In fact, teacher-student relationship is supportive of learner or student-centred education, makes case for a closer teacher-student tie in the course of teaching and learning or a positive relationship between the teacher and the student, increases students' engagement with studies as well as serves as a protective shield for students at the edge of failure or decline in their academic pursuits.

What has been said above is a pointer that teacher-student relationship can be associated with many positive and negative capabilities or more technically is a foundation of whatever good or bad that happens in the school or in educational institutions. We need to have it at the back of our minds that the quality of teacher-student relationship, the quality of leadership and obedience to rules and regulations in schools and educational institutions is directly and indirectly impacted or influenced by the quality of teacher-student relationship in any particular school. Because of this, positive and negative capabilities of teacher-student relationship have become flashpoints that scholars focus exclusive attention on. According to Goktas and Kuya (2023:277), positive teacher-student relationship is described as those types of teacher-student relationships that are characterized by high intimacy and low conflicts and dependency. According to them, positive teacher-student relationship is easier to establish when the teacher pays close attention to the students. This position had earlier been established by Suryani (2018), who writes that

positive teacher-student relationship develops when the teacher understands his student and goes further to write that positive teacher-student relationship is an open communication between teachers and students whose indexes includes mutual acceptance, warmth, understanding, trust, closeness, support, respect, cooperation and care.

Positive teacher-student relationship is beneficial in many ways, it enhances students' academic achievement, it boosts students' confidence, provides students with the ability and capability to address, redress and overcome whatever inferiority complex they may have that may have negatively impacted on their academic pursuits. On the other hand, positive teacher-student relationship according to Ganguly (2014), Odegard, Pesonen and Solberg (2025) promotes positive learning environment, strengthens academic and social development as well as helps to decrease the frequency of disruptive behaviour among students or learners.

The teacher who promotes positive teacher-student relationship in the school systematically develops the student along cognitive, social, emotional and moral trajectories where the students develop attitudes towards their studies that enhance their academic achievement, develop receptive and robust attitudes towards school, develop confidence and trust in themselves that are capable of repositioning them in readiness for addressing any challenge in the world. Teacher-student relationship is especially unique in providing students safeguard that can enhance their adjustment to academic pursuit and redefinition of themselves in the school in particular and the world generally. Teacher-student relationship deepens teachers' insight and brightens their lens and visions on issues of care, confidence and trust which are at the heart of teaching and learning. Teachers traditionally as parents (what is technically referred to as in-loco parentis) to students serve as parent to learners but teacher-student relationship helps to strengthen their care, confidence and trust dimension in teaching and learning sessions.

Teacher-student relationship enables teachers to identify interventionist strategies to use on students especially those who struggle with their studies. Through Teacher-student relationship, teachers can understand better the behavioural and attitudinal dispositions of students particularly those behaviours and attitudes towards students from teachers that students view to be embarrassing.

Teacher-student relationship helps to minimize the occurrence of disruptive and other behaviours that are anti-thetical to harmonious social existence in the classroom and in the school. The awareness and realization that a teacher who relates well with a disruptive student can be angry with the student when he hears of the student's disruptive behaviour has some strong powers to checkmate the disruptive behaviour of the student. Positive teacher-student relationship especially for students who have benefitted from the many services that teachers render such as mentoring and counselling opens up opportunities through which students appreciate the effort of their teachers in their academic and general development.

On the other hand, negative teacher-student relationship is that type of relationship between a teacher and a student that is excessively characterized by low intimacy and high conflict and dependency (Pianta 2001, Pianta & Stullhman 2004, Hughes 2011). Put slightly different, Ganguly (2014) writes that negative teacher-student relationship is characterized by unhealthy relations that inherently have potentials to hinder the socio-emotional development of the student or learner. What is visible in a negative teacher-student relationship is a strained, abusive, violent, not -too-good and conflictual relationship, which produces detrimental consequences especially insinuation in students that start to make them feel misunderstood, ignored or unfairly treated (Nguyen, 2025) and correspondingly cause them to begin to exhibit defiance, withdrawal, show of conflict and disengagement or anxiety which at the final analysis negatively affect their learning.

Strategies for making Teacher-Student Relationship a Reality in Educational Institutions

No doubt teaching and learning in particular and education generally is an activity in which positive relationship is central and key for attaining the core mandates of teaching and learning or education. The truth of the centrality of positive relationship between the teacher and the student in teaching and learning or education can be acknowledged in the recognition that teaching and learning or education globally is a relational activity, without which two persons who are critical stakeholders in teaching and learning, who are different persons, who share different values, who share different beliefs, different religions and come

from different backgrounds may not cooperatively work together. True, positive relationship is at the heart of teaching and learning or education generally, however, in all its multi-faceted nature, a high priority is always given to positive teacher-student relationship which Suryani (2014:264) acknowledges is very difficult to build. The above observation can be pointing in the direction that teacher-student relationship may be poorly existing or may not exist at all in some educational institutions.

Positive teacher-student relationship holds the keys for illuminating and bringing about all the empowering, emancipating, liberating, radical and revolutionary reforms and transformations that are associated with teaching and learning or education for short, but what leaves a better taste in the mouth and at the same time is a cause for concern for genuine practitioners in the field of education is the open secret that many practitioners in the field of education hardly integrate or incorporate positive teacher-student relationship strategies in their teaching and learning practices. This is a pointer that many practitioners in teaching and learning in particular and education generally may have been compromising to the point of operating without prioritizing, what every practitioner, what every school, what every educational personnel and what every educational institution should make a topmost priority. On the basis of this observation, this section of the study provides detailed insights on some of the strategies that can make teacher-student relationship a reality or a norm in educational institutions.

Positive teacher-student relationship is at the heart of teaching and learning and teachers who are most productive and impactful on students and the large society are those teachers who recognize the role of positive relationship in removing all variables that constitute themselves into barriers and obstacles in teaching and learning or in the education industry. On the other hand, teachers who make the least impacts on students and the larger society are those teachers who ignore the centrality of teacher-student relationship in their professional practices. What has been said above, situates the teacher as one of the principal persons upon which most of the actions and activities that target promoting positive teacher-student relationship revolves around. This is not a surprise because the teacher is central and critical in the entire learning process in educational institutions as the extent in which he builds trust, confidence, develops caring spirit, puts up supportive relationships with students, draws students closer to himself and plays the roles of parents to the students, goes a long way in redirecting the epistemological, metaphysical and axiological outlooks of the students into developing positive teacher-student relationship with him. Specifically, teachers who care and who develops caring attitudes for their students consciously and unconsciously lay foundations for what Zhan (2025) calls the cornerstone for fostering teacher-student relationship.

This means a teacher who is desirous of making teacher-student relationship a norm can undergo various re-orientation where more than anything else, his values for caring for the students climbs up to the highest level or becomes his highest priority. This is because students as special breed of the society hold anyone who values them in high esteem and can go extra miles to respect, obey and cooperate with such a person. Attempts to value the students can follow trajectories where the teacher shows phenomenal interests in the academic, social, moral, career and general development of the student, demonstrates to the student that he has confidence, love and trust for him, where the teacher invents and innovates ideas that try to satisfy the curiosity of the student as well as provides relevant experiences or instructions that can support the student into meeting his needs or achieving his short and long term goals.

A teacher can prioritize the promotion of teacher-student relationship by striving to identify the strengths, needs, interests, likes and dislikes of the students. As a way of demonstrating his concern for the students, he can know all his students by their names, have regular discussions with the students about their homes and can relate what he teaches to the experiences of the students in their various homes. A teacher who is desirous of developing good positive relationship with his students can consistently play down his ego or jettison the culture where it is the norm that the younger person must first greet the elder. In a case where one is interested in fostering positive teacher-student relationship, the teacher can be the first to greet his students and his attempts at this can help him identify introverts and extroverts among his students as well as identify sound pedagogical strategies for ensuring that students in any side of the divide benefit from his wealth of experience. Teachers who are desirous of promoting positive teacher-student relations can strive to align themselves with the needs and preferences of the students. As earlier pointed out, students

easily develop relationship with people who value them and taking this into consideration, teachers can find time to be discussing with their students on strategies for building positive teacher-student relationship particularly those students who usually feel shy and withdrawn from fellow students and social activities in the society. A teacher who succeeds in breaking the above jinx in his student has removed a major obstacle and a major obstruction that can impair the educational and social progress of the student.

In addition, teachers who show concern in promoting teacher-student relationship can do so by integrating elements of humour in their dealings with the students. True, learning is an abstract activity that requires some moments of comic relief, in which case, the teacher's ability to introduce some elements of humour can positively create windows for self-reflection that can provide guide and direction for understanding what has been taught to them. The point here is that humour is a necessary and fundamental foundation for relaxing tension, creating scenes that can stimulate recalling and remembrance as well as opportunity for self-awareness in students particularly in teaching and learning session.

Related to the fact above is that any teacher who makes teacher-student relationship a topmost priority can equally make the display of behavioural dispositions that hold cultural sensitivity and cultural responsiveness in high regard in his dealings with the students. What this means is that the teacher can create environment that in all ramifications is safe for every student in the classroom, without any form of intimidation or bias against the culture of any learner in the classroom. Situations where teachers praise the cultures of some students in the classroom and undermine the cultures of others send signals that have potentials to block teacher-student relationship. This is because such behaviours amount to disrespecting and undervaluing the cultures of some of the students and no student likes this. We have earlier stated that students easily and quickly identify with whoever values them, consequently any teacher who is conscious of promoting positive teacher-student relationship can consistently applaud those students, who in their behaviours and efforts consistently meet up those standards expected of students. Such compliments and words of support mean a lot to students and students usually relate well with teachers who praise, acknowledge and sing their achievements.

Teachers who have thorough grasp of their discipline or teachers who have high level of professional credibility make phenomenal impacts that are solid on their students and this excellence in the mastery of their discipline opens wide roads for positive teacher-student relationship between such teachers and their students. So, teachers who are desirous of promoting positive teacher-student relationship can intensify efforts to up their games by sharpening their disciplinary expertise and pedagogical acumen (Zhan, 2025) and this development has multiplier effects for the teacher and the entire school system namely; it challenges teachers to continuously intensify mastery of subject matter and this positively impacts on the quality of the products they release to the society for the development of the state. Related to good knowledge of the teacher's subject matter is the ability of the teacher who is desirous of positive teacher-student relationship not to compromise on those qualities of trust, care, love, reliability, consistency and closeness, which he tries to promote in the students. In fact, the teacher should be a role model whose character students should pray to emulate and not one person who can tell students one thing and be engaged in another.

True, we have laid emphasis on attitudinal and behavioural dispositions that teachers can display in their quest and desire to make teacher-student relationship a norm in educational institutions, however there are other stakeholders in educational institutions and the society whose roles, actions and activities are essential in making teacher-student relationship a reality. The school as a social institution has critical roles to play in efforts to promote good teacher-student relationship and the school can achieve this through the creation of a supportive school culture. According to Zhan (2025:225), schools and educational institutions can create cultures that are conducive and supportive of positive teacher-student relationship when they create a positive, united, fraternal and respectful campus cultural atmosphere, which can come to fruition through what he calls "themed class meetings, campus cultural festivals and teacher ethic speech contests". Schools and educational institutions can make teacher-student relationship a norm through providing opportunities for strengthening teacher's managerial and epistemological base. Prioritizing and enhancing the managerial and epistemological base of the teacher can enhance the

productive impact of the teacher and boost the functionality of the students. We have maintained that students robustly and receptively identify with teachers whose knowledge and expertise bring about reforms and transformations in their lives. Teacher-student relationship can be promoted through the attitudes of the members of the society and the state towards education generally and the teacher in particular. Any society or state that values education is directly acknowledging the importance of education and the teacher, and such value and respect for education and the teacher has potential to influence the way people regard education, teaching, and the teacher. Holding education and the teaching profession in high esteem or high regard has the capacity to trigger in students the curiosity to connect with the teacher for career guide, especially those students who wish to become teachers. The fact is clear and simple that students who admire the respect that education generally and the teacher in particular enjoys on the national priority list of the state can systematically prioritize initiating teacher-student relationships early during the earliest period of their education especially on possible prospects and career trajectories in education and teaching. The route for translating all this into reality is a robust teacher-student relationship.

The family from where these students come from can play supportive roles in promoting teacher-student relationships. Families can help to trigger and connect these all-important interactions or relationships between the teacher and the student when families identify strongly with the actions and activities of schools, a development that can enable families keep and maintain close surveillance on activities that go on in the school, especially on students' activities that go on in the school, particularly students' responses to their studies or the level of correspondence between the expectations of the society from learning experiences that have been impacted on students and reality. Believing that there may be compromise or areas that may need some improvements, and this comes to the knowledge of the school management and the students, such awareness can signal new directions for administrative and managerial overhaul and robust teacher-student relationship or interaction, which in the final analysis can point in directions that can pave ways for cooperative resolution of any impediments or limitations that may be identified.

CONCLUSION

One major focus that makes education a global pursuit is that states irrespective of their developmental sophistication or lack of it look up to education for direction and guidance on the next line of actions for raising the required human capital that can enable states to translate their dreams and aspirations of national development into reality. The dreams and aspirations of every state to develop or make lasting and sustainable impacts on the indexes for determining national development strongly lies on the quality of human capital that any state can boost of. The link between human capital and national development is premised on the fact that human beings are the carriers of the genes that radically, revolutionally and transformatively trigger development. Naturally, in the quest and desire of states to position themselves in readiness for national development, focus is usually placed on raising the right human capital that can trigger that national development. This is where education through the teacher and the student occupies the centre stage of such discussions. The teacher cannot be under-estimated in discussions that revolve around knowledge construction, knowledge generation, knowledge dissemination and human capital development that are at the heart of the national development of states. The teacher is usually at the centre of discussions about states that want to make headway through education and human capital development and it is the teacher who educates the student. The student is the real agent of change for the various reforms and transformations whose sustenance trigger and lead to national development, so visible that he acts as the vessel and instrument for actualizing whatever visions and aspirations the leaders of the state have for the development of the state. It is acknowledged that whatever was not done properly and whatever innovations that can be fixed in the present time for achieving the dreams of a people and their state can be routed or channelled through the school or educational institutions via the teacher and the student.

The above reveals that the teacher and the student are critical focal flashpoints in human capital development and national development of states. These critical roles of the teacher and the student in human capital development and national development of states begin in the classroom and the extent in

which the combined efforts of the teacher and the student translate to national development of the state is heavily dependent on how robust, receptive and rich teacher-student relationship in teaching and learning sessions in the classroom and other activities that take place in educational institutions can be, but clear evidence and indications show that there is phenomenal and epic poor teacher student relationship in classrooms and educational institutions, an unfortunate development that has been responsible for education and products of educational institutions not living up to expectations and states not recording expected levels of national development.

This downward trend in teacher-student relationship in classrooms and educational institutions is an unfortunate development that seriously needs to be addressed very urgently through some pragmatic actions. Teachers can be sensitized to acknowledge that the responsibility of making teacher-student relationship a norm in the classroom or in educational institutions majorly and principally falls within their jurisdiction and teachers can equally be sensitized to acknowledge that majority of them terribly lack the knowledge and skills for practicing or making teacher-student relation a norm in the classroom and in educational institutions. As no one can practice what he has no ideas of or give to another what he does not have, this foundational and fundamental flaw maybe revealing a professional deficiency in the line of the education of the teacher and a terrible lack of foresight on the part of stakeholders in education that can only be corrected and remedied through repositioning teacher education.

Undermining the prioritization of teacher-student relationship is a fundamental neglect of what should be prioritized in any effective and functional classroom, educational system and teacher education programme that targets national development. Reviving this unfortunate development can be one where teacher education institutions start to introduce innovations particularly in curriculum and pedagogy and in the new curriculum develop new courses that can align with the reality of the twenty-first century especially those realities that can bring about quality human capital development that can translate into robust national development. The new order can play down the excessive conservatism in teacher education with its associated fear and lack of creativity and critical thinking especially among practitioners, but in the new vision, efforts can be made to encourage practitioners to embrace innovations that are support of empowering teachers for sustainable national development. Repositioning teacher education along this line has potentials to add value to teachers by professionally empowering them and making them relevance in national development discourse.

Such new courses can sensitize the teacher that in addition to his educational qualifications, he practically needs to develop behavioral dispositions where the priority can be on the development and demonstration of moral virtues such as trust, confidence, self-discipline, empathy and ethics of care for the students. The inculcation of the development of these moral values by the teacher and their genuine demonstration towards the students can be foundations upon which the teacher's productivity, professional growth and positive contributions to human capital development upon which the national development of the state can depend. One the other hand, where teacher student relationship is made a norm, it has potentials to lay foundations where academic achievements among students can be higher. In fact, teacher-student relationship enhances teacher professional development and commitment as well as improves students' scholarly engagement, academic achievement and moral development.

New developments in classroom practice in particular and in educational institutions generally may be restructured to follow trajectories where teachers can be re-educated along lines where they internalize new orientations and in the new orientations, teachers can be sensitized to place high values on their students through making teacher-student relationship a norm. This development is a demonstration of show of value for the student and when students recognize that their teachers value them, such developments can cause students to reciprocate by morally submitting, obeying and demonstrating the highest form of loyalty to rules and regulations put up by the teacher. In fact, the more important aspect of this is that it helps to lay solid foundations for robust harmonious co-existence between teachers and students especially the ability of students to express themselves, provides guideposts for guiding students on career paths, development of students' personality and the ability of students to choose their role models from their teachers. Developing curriculum that empowers students to express themselves has pedagogical implications namely, teachers easily and quickly understand feelings, emotions and areas of

difficulties of the students and correspondingly match same with new strategies that can be beneficial to students, a development that can add to the professional growth of the teacher and the teacher's commitment to building a strong human capital base for the national development of the state.

Schools and educational institutions can play fundamental and foundational roles that can support teacher student relationship through consciously creating and providing the right environment where constant interaction between the teacher and the learners can be a norm. Again, achieving teacher student relationship can be possible when the teacher demonstrates his professional expertise through structuring his instructions along lines where learning becomes a fun and a thing to be enjoyed by the student. The teacher can be sensitized to value his students and this singular act can lay sound foundations for sustainable teacher student relationship. In fact, we can strongly say it that any school or educational institution that wants to be more functional and impactful on students and through this way contribute meaningfully to the human capital and national development of the state can embrace and make teacher student relationship a norm.

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